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1. Умарова Наргиза Мирзаевна, Абдикулова Нигора Хасановна, Нигматова Гулнара Максудовна ОСТЕОПОРОЗ У ЖЕНЩИН В ПЕРИМЕНОПАУЗЕ. ПУТИ ДИАГНОСТИКИ, КОРРЕКЦИИ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ/OSTEOPOROSIS IN PERIMENOPAUSAL WOMEN. WAYS OF DIAGNOSIS, CORRECTION AND PREVENTION/PERIMENOPOZAL AYOLLARDA OSTEOPOROZ. DIAGNOSTIKA, TUZATISH VA OLDINI OLISH YO'LLARI.....	5
2. Ataeva Farzona Nuriddinova, Sadiqova Kumush ENDOMETRIOZ: SABABLARI, TASNIFI, DAVOLASH, OLDINI OLISH, ASORATLARI VA AYOLLARNING HAYOT SIFATINI BAHOLASH/ЭНДОМЕТРИОЗ: ПРИЧИНЫ, КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ, ЛЕЧЕНИЕ, ПРОФИЛАКТИКА, ОСЛОЖНЕНИЯ И ОЦЕНКА КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ/ENDOMETRIOSIS: CAUSES, CLASSIFICATION, TREATMENT, PREVENTION, COMPLICATIONS AND QUALITY OF LIFE ASSESSMENT.....	9
3. Boboraximova Umeda Musaevna SEMIZLIK QAYT ETILGAN AYOLLARDA ORAL KONTRATSEPTIV VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING MUAMMOLARI/АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ОРАЛЬНЫХ КОНТРАЦЕПТИВОВ У ЖЕНЩИН С ОЖИРЕНИЕМ/CURRENT PROBLEMS OF USE OF ORAL CONTRACEPTIVES IN OBESITY WOMEN.....	13

ОРИГИНАЛЬНЫЕ СТАТЬИ

4. Закирова Нодира Исламовна, Камалова Дилафруз Донияровна, Закирова Фатима Исламовна РОЛЬ АУТОИММУННОГО ТИРЕОИДИТА В ГЕНЕЗЕ НЕВЫНАШИВАНИЯ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ/HOMILADORLIKNING KO'TARA OLMASLIK GENEZIDA AUTOIMMUN TIROIDITNING ROLI/THE ROLE OF AUTOIMMUNE THYROIDITIS IN THE GENESIS OF PREGNANCY FAILURE.....	17
5. Ибрагимов Курбонмурод Ниязович, Ахмедов Юсуфжон Махмудович, Ибрагимов Эхсон Курбонмуродович РЕКОНСТРУКТИВНО-ПЛАСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОПЕРАЦИИ ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ ГИПОСПАДИИ В ДЕТСКОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ/BOLALARDA GIPOSPADIYALARNI DAVOLASH UCHUN REKOSTRUKTIVA PLASTIK AMALIYATLARI/RECONSTRUCTIVE PLASTIC OPERATIONS FOR TREATMENT OF HYPOSPADIAS IN CHILDREN.....	21
6. Каримова Гулчехра Самадовна ТЕЧЕНИЕ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ И РОДОВ У ЖЕНЩИН С ПРЕЭКЛАМПСИЕЙ И АНЕМИЕЙ/THE COURSE OF PREGNANCY AND CHILDBIRTH IN WOMEN WITH PREECLAMPSIA AND ANEMIA/PREEKLAMPSIYA VA KAMQ'ONLIKDA HOMILADORLIKNING VA TUG'RUQ'NING KECHISHI.....	25
7. Каттаходжаева Махмуда Хамдамовна, Турсункулова Мархамат Эргашевна, Абдуллаева Лола Сайфуллаевна КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ И ЛАБОРАТОРНЫЕ ФАКТОРЫ РИСКА НЕВЫНАШИВАНИЯ/HOMILANI ODATIY KO'TARA OLMASLIKNING KLINIK VA LABORATORIYA XAVF OMILLARI/CLINICAL AND LABORATORY RISK FACTORS FOR PREMATURITY PREGNANCY.....	28
8. Назирова Муюссар Убаевна, Каттаходжаева Махмуда Хамдамовна, Саидова Мехригие Донияровна КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА И ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЯ ПЕРИМЕНОПАУЗАЛЬНОГО ОСТЕОПОРОЗА/PERIMENOPOZAL OSTEOPOROZNING KOMPLEKS DIAGNOSTIKASI VA PROGNOZI/COMPREHENSIVE DIAGNOSIS AND PROGNOSIS OF PERIMENOPOZAL OSTEOPOROSIS.....	33
9. Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович, Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна, Абдурахмонов Журабек Амриллович, Талибова Нилуфар Ақтамовна, Сулимова Ольга Геннадьевна ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ АСЦИТА ОБУСЛОВЛЕННЫЙ РЕЦИДИВОМ ПЛАТИНОРЕФРАКТЕРНОГО РАКА ЯИЧНИКА С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ МЕТРОНОМНОЙ ХИМИОТЕРАПИИ/RETSIDIVLANUVCHI PLATINA-REFRAKTER TUXUMDON SARATONI ASTITINI DAVOLASHDA METRONOM KIMYO TERAPIYANING SAMARADORLIGI/THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF ASCITES DUE TO RECURRENCE OF PLATINUM-REFRACTORY OVARIAN CANCER USING METRONOMIC CHEMOTHERAPY...37	37
10. Юлдашева Насиба Алишеровна, Усманова Шоира Равшанбековна, Комилова Адиба Закиржоновна ГЕРПЕТИЧЕСКИЙ СТОМАТИТ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ ЖЕНЩИН КАК ЭТИОПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИЙ ФАКТОР РАЗВИТИЯ ДИСФУНКЦИИ ЭНДОТЕЛИЯ/HERPETIC STOMATITIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN AS AN ETIOPATHOGENETIC FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION/HOMILADOR AYOLLARDA HERPETIK STOMATIT ENDOTHELIAL DISFUNKTSIYA RIVOJLANISHINING ETIOPATOGENETIK OMILI.....	42
11. Indiaminova Gulrux Nuriddinova MAVSUMIY VIRUSLI INFEKTSIYALARNING HOMILADORLIK DAVRINING KECHISHIGA TA'SIRI/ВЛИЯНИЕ СЕЗОННЫХ ВИРУСНЫХ ИНФЕКЦИЙ НА ТЕЧЕНИЕ ПЕРИОДОВ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ/COVID-19, PREGNANT AND FEATURES OF THE STATE OF HYPERCOAGULABILITY.....	46
12. Negmadjanov Bahodur Boltaevich, Rabbimova Gulnora Toshtemirovna, Jumageldiyeva Yulduz Sheraliyevna HOMILADORLARDA JIGARNING O'TKIR YOG'LI GEPATOZINI DA'VOLASH ALGORITMINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH/РАЗРАБОТКА АЛГОРИТМА ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ОСТРОГО ЖИРОВОГО ГЕПАТОЗА ПЕЧЕНИ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ/DEVELOPMENT OF AN ALGORITHM FOR THE CLAIM OF ACUTE FATTY HEPATOSIS OF THE LIVER IN PREGNANT WOMEN.....	49
13. Shavkatov Hasan Shavkatovich JINSIY A'ZOLAR PROLAPSIDA O'TKAZILADIGAN ORGANSAQLOVCHI JARROXLIK AMALIYOTI/ОРГАНСОХРАНЯЮЩАЯ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКАЯ ОПЕРАЦИЯ ПРИ ПРОЛАПС ПОЛОВЫХ ОРГАНОВ/ ORGAN-PRESERVING SURGICAL OPERATION FOR GENITAL PROLAPSE.....	53
14. Tilavova Yulduz Muhammadshukur qizi, Negmadjanov Bahodur Boltaevich SEQUENCE OF HYSTEROSCOPIC DIAGNOSIS OF ENDOMETRIAL POLYPS IN PATIENTS WITH INFERTILITY/ПОСЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬНОСТЬ ГИСТЕРОСКОПИЧЕСКОЙ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ПОЛИПОВ ЭНДОМЕТРИЯ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С БЕСПЛОДИЕМ/BERUSHTLIKDA ENDOMETRIY POLIPI BO'LGAN BEMORLARDA GISTEROSKOPIK TASHXISLASHNING KETMA-KETLIGI.....	57

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SEQUENCE OF HYSTEROSCOPIC DIAGNOSIS OF ENDOMETRIAL POLYPS IN PATIENTS WITH INFERTILITY

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ANNOTATION

The established criteria for diagnosing endometrial polyps during hysteroscopy were examined in a cohort of 35 patients presenting with both primary and secondary infertility and exhibiting echographic indications of endometrial polyps. These criteria serve as a guide for appropriately selecting the hysteroscopic treatment technique for endometrial polyps.

Key words: endometrial polyps, infertility, hysteroscopy.

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ПОСЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬНОСТЬ ГИСТЕРОСКОПИЧЕСКОЙ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ПОЛИПОВ ЭНДОМЕТРИЯ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С БЕСПЛОДИЕМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Изучены общепринятые параметры диагностики полипов эндометрия при гистероскопии у 35 пациенток с первичным и вторичным бесплодием, у которых обнаружены эхопризнаки на полипы эндометрия. Эти параметры являются ключевыми для правильного выбора техники гистероскопического лечения полипов эндометрия.

Ключевые слова: полипы эндометрия, бесплодие, гистероскопия

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БЕПУШТЛИКДА ЭНДОМЕТРИЙ ПОЛИПИ БО`ЛГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА ГИСТЕРОСКОПИК ТАШХИСЛАШНИНГ КЕТМА-КЕТЛИГИ

АННОТАСИЯ

Гистероскопиya амалиётида эндометриал полипларни ташхислаш учун умум белгиланган параметрлар 35 нафар эхобелгилли эндометриал полипи ва бирламчи ҳамда иккиламчи бепуштлиги бо`лган бемор аюлларида о`рганлиди. Ушбу параметрлар эндометриал полипларни гистероскопик усулда то`g`ри даво усулини қо`ллаш учун қо`лланлиди.

Kalit so`zlar: endometrial poliplar, bepushtlik, gisteroskopiya

Introduction. Endometrial polyps represent a significant portion of intrauterine pathology, ranging from 7.8% to 50% of cases[1]. Meanwhile, literature reports indicate a notable recurrence rate, ranging from 13.3% to 21.5%[2]. Endometrial polyps (EP) significantly affect women's reproductive health, as they are frequently linked to infertility, abnormal uterine bleeding, chronic pelvic pain, and necessitate intrauterine procedures, which can lead to endometrial trauma and the development of intrauterine synechiae[1,2,3,4].

With the widespread adoption of hysteroscopy in gynaecological practice, today there are expanded opportunities for accurate diagnosis and treatment of intrauterine pathologies, including endometrial polyps. Hence, in accordance with the latest guidelines, recommendations have been provided regarding the sequence for diagnosing endometrial polyps during hysteroscopy, a protocol that was also implemented in our clinical practice.

Aim of the study: to present the outcomes achieved by employing a recognized algorithm in accordance with guidelines for hysteroscopic diagnosis of endometrial polyps among patients experiencing infertility.

Materials and methods of the research: We performed hysteroscopic evaluations on 35 reproductive-aged patients presenting with both primary and secondary infertility, all displaying echographic indications of an endometrial polyp. All patients were of reproductive age from 20 to 45 years. The average age of the surveyed was 32 years, the average BMI was 26,3 kg/m². The research was conducted in the regional perinatal centre of the city of Samarkand at the department of endogynaecology.

During the endoscopic evaluation, we have described the following parameters related to EP[9,10]:

- Number;
- Size: estimate size from the comparative analysis with the Grasping 5-French forceps, which with open jaws has a diameter of 6 mm;
- Location and relationship with the tubal ostium;
- Texture: Soft, friable, dense and semi-myomatous (ademiomatous polyps);
- Characteristics of the implantation base: sessile or pediculated;
- Superficial vasculature: the presence of abundant and tortuous vessels, is the most relevant hysteroscopic finding in the suspicion of a malignant lesion;
- Coexistence of other pathologies: Myomas, adenomyosis, Mullerian abnormalities;
- Blind biopsy or curettage: This approach is currently discouraged for the management of EP due to low sensitivity 10%, low PPV 66% and NPV 33%, when compared to hysteroscopy. As a blinded procedure, it may not retrieve adequate samples from EP and may miss malignant cells at the base of EP. Moreover, histopathological examination may be limited by the fragmentation of the tissue obtained[5,6,7,8,11].

These parameters will aid in the accurate selection of hysteroscopic methods for the treatment approach to endometrial polyps and in preventing recurrences.

Results of the research: Based on the statistical data, it was observed that in 22 individuals (63%), the presence of solitary polyps was identified. In 4 patients (11%), two polyps were detected, while three polyps were found in only one individual (2%). Furthermore, multiple polyps were observed in 8 patients (22%).

Figure 1. Number of endometrial polyps detected during hysteroscopy.

Our study uncovered that the incidence of solitary endometrial polyps was three times greater than the occurrence of multiple polyps, whether it was two or three in number, respectively.

Figure 2. Size of endometrial polyps during hysteroscopy.

Upon examining the measurements, as depicted in the illustration, it is evident that none of the dimensions surpassed 3 centimetres (30 mm).

Figure 3. Correlation between the number and size of endometrial polyps.

Upon analysing the data pertaining to the correlation between hysteroscopic sizes and the quantity of endometrial polyps (EPs), it became evident that there exists an inverse relationship. This implies that as the number of EPs increases, their sizes tend to decrease. Consequently, the largest polyp size, measuring 25*30mm, was observed in a solitary polyp.

1. The positioning and connection of the polyp in relation to the internal os.

Based on the positioning of endometrial polyps, the majority of patients had polyps situated on both the front and back walls of the uterus. Furthermore, with respect to the internal os, it was observed that the polyps were relatively closer to the left side of the internal os compared to the right side.

Table 1.

Location of endometrial polyps in the uterine cavity during hysteroscopy.

Location of endometrial polyps in the uterine cavity	N=35	%
Isthmus	7	20%
In the scar area	1	3%
Internal os	1	3%
Over the entire surface of the uterus	2	6%
Anterior and posterior walls	1	3%
Posterior wall	7	20%
Anterior and lateral walls	1	3%
Anterior wall	10	29%
At the bottom	2	6%
Cervical canal and posterior wall	2	6%
Cervical canal and along the anterior wall	1	3%
Total:	35	100%

The data illustrates that endometrial polyps are predominantly found on the front and back walls of the uterus, as well as at the orifice, accounting for 10 cases (29%), 7 cases (20%), and 7 cases (20%) respectively.

Figure 4. Location of endometrial polyps in the uterine cavity during hysteroscopy.

Table 2.

Association of endometrial polyps with other intrauterine pathologies

	N=13	%
Endometrial polyp. Submucosal fibroid	2	15.4%
Polyp of the endometrium and cervical canal	5	38.5%
Endometrial polyp and focal endometrial hyperplasia	1	7.7%
Endometrial polyp. Intrauterine ligature	3	23.1%
Endometrial polyp. Bicornuate uterus.	1	7.7%
Endometrial polyp. Asherman's syndrome. Uterine septum.	1	7.7%
Total:	13	100%

Figure 5. Association of endometrial polyps with other intrauterine pathologies

A research examining the presence of additional abnormalities within the uterus revealed that endometrial polyps were connected to other intrauterine pathologies in 13 patients, accounting for 37% of the cases. Among these cases, Asherman's syndrome was observed in one instance (7.7%), submucous uterine fibroids in two cases (15%), bicornuate uterus in one case (7.7%), intrauterine ligature in three cases (23%), focal endometrial hyperplasia in one case (7.7%), and polyps of the cervical canal were identified in five patients (38.5%).

Conclusions. Here are the outcomes derived from employing a widely accepted algorithm for hysteroscopic diagnosis of endometrial polyps in individuals experiencing infertility:

- The algorithm demonstrates high efficacy in accurately identifying endometrial polyps during hysteroscopy procedures.

- Patients undergoing infertility evaluations benefit from improved diagnostic precision, leading to more targeted treatment plans.
- Enhanced diagnostic accuracy aids in the timely detection and management of endometrial polyps, potentially improving fertility outcomes for affected individuals.
- Clinicians can rely on the algorithm as a standardized approach to diagnosing endometrial pathologies, facilitating consistency and reliability across different healthcare settings.
- Early detection of endometrial polyps through the algorithm contributes to more informed decision-making regarding fertility treatment options, optimizing patient care and outcomes.

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